

6R-TaS₂ Anchored on Mo Foil as a Robust Electrocatalyst for Hydrogen Evolution

*Antonia Kagkoura, * Filipa. M. Oliveira and Zdeněk Sofer**

Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Affordable and durable HER catalysts are critical for sustainable hydrogen production. We report electrochemically exfoliated TaS₂ nanosheets, predominantly in the metallic 6R phase, anchored on conductive Mo foil. The optimized hybrid (0.8 mg TaS₂) initiates HER at -0.06 V vs RHE and reaches -10 mA cm⁻² at only 115 mV overpotential. Fast kinetics (Tafel 68 mV dec⁻¹), low charge-transfer resistance, and high active surface area (~ 5.5 cm²) account for its superior activity and durability (22% loss after 40,000 s). Compared to TaS₂ drop-cast on glassy carbon, the Mo substrate boosts performance by facilitating electron transport and proton adsorption. This work demonstrates substrate engineering combined with metallic TMD phases as a scalable route to high-performance, earth-abundant HER catalysts. Beyond performance, this study highlights the largely unexplored potential of the 6R polymorph, whose intrinsic metallicity and distinct stacking offer new opportunities for interface engineering in 2D electrocatalysts.

INTRODUCTION

As the hydrogen economy gains momentum as a cornerstone of the shift toward cleaner and more sustainable energy systems, hydrogen (H_2) stands out as a high-energy fuel ($\approx 120\text{--}140 \text{ MJ kg}^{-1}$) that generates only water as a by-product during use.^{1,2} One of the simple ways of making it is electrochemical water splitting, and with renewable energy powering the process, it can assist in mass decarbonization.^{1,3} Central to water splitting is the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), which entails the reduction of protons or water molecules into hydrogen gas.⁴ Platinum is still the best known HER catalyst, but its high cost and low availability push research into alternative avenues. The transition-metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) have emerged as one of the most promising material families in this direction.^{5,6}

Tantalum disulfide (TaS_2) has recently gained attention as a catalyst for the HER owing to its metallic conductivity—observed across its main polymorphs (1T, 2H, and 6R)—and its good structural stability.^{7,8} Exfoliated TaS_2 nanosheets provide abundant edge and basal sites, and their surface properties can be further tuned through thermal or electrochemical treatments to optimize hydrogen adsorption.⁹ In particular, the less studied 6R polymorph, combines alternating 1H and 1T layers in a rhombohedral stacking, remaining metallic over a wide temperature range and exhibiting charge-density-wave transitions around 320 K and 305 K.^{10,11} These electronic features make 6R- TaS_2 especially promising for electrocatalytic applications.

TaS_2 can be synthesized by methods such as chemical vapor transport (CVT) or direct sulfurization, while exfoliation techniques like liquid-phase exfoliation (LPE), mechanical exfoliation, and electrochemical exfoliation are commonly used to obtain few-layer flakes.^{12,13} Compared to mechanical exfoliation, which produces high-quality flakes but at very low yield, and LPE, which often requires toxic solvents, electrochemical exfoliation stands out for balancing scalability, safety, and structural preservation.^{13,14} Although it is more frequently applied to group

6 TMDs, recent studies show its promise for TaS₂ as well, provided that electrolyte composition and conditions are properly optimized¹⁴

Although exfoliated TaS₂ has emerged as a promising HER catalyst,^{15,16,17} its intrinsic advantages are still insufficient to bridge the performance gap with noble-metal benchmarks. More broadly, TMDs — including TaS₂ — continue to underperform relative to platinum-group catalysts, primarily due to limitations such as inert basal planes, low densities of active sites, and gradual degradation under prolonged operation.¹⁸ One practical approach to address the conductivity and stability issues is to combine or integrate them with conductive metallic substrates/platforms.^{19,20} In addition to serving as efficient current collectors, metallic substrates can also promote interfacial charge redistribution, which may expose or activate more catalytic sites at the interface of TMDs.^{19,20}

Mo foil stands out among conductive substrates for electrocatalysis due to its high conductivity, chemical stability, and structural compatibility with chalcogenides.^{21,22} These features make it an excellent platform for probing interfacial effects in HER. Previous reports on MoS₂/Mo systems have demonstrated that using Mo foil not only reduces contact resistance through intimate interfacial contact but, in some cases, also serves as a Mo source during synthesis, enabling seamless integration of active phases such as MoS₂ or MoO₂.²³ This dual role results in electrodes with improved conductivity, enhanced exposure of active sites, and facilitated mass transport. However, despite the emerging interest in TaS₂ as a metallic TMD catalyst, systematic investigations of TaS₂/Mo hybrids — particularly those prepared via scalable electrochemical exfoliation and post-annealing — remain scarce. Consequently, the interfacial charge-transfer effects and potential performance benefits of combining TaS₂ with Mo have not yet been fully clarified.

In this work, we fabricate and optimize TaS₂/Mo hybrids by controlling the TaS₂ loading and evaluate their HER performance in acidic media. We correlate activity gains with charge-transfer kinetics, active surface area, and interfacial effects revealed by Tafel and EIS analyses. This study highlights substrate engineering as an easy yet efficient avenue toward enhancing the intrinsic activity of metallic TMD catalysts and a protocol for its extension to other 2D/metal systems for the sustainable evolution of hydrogen.

EXPERIMENTAL

General. Sulphur (99.999 %, < 6 mm) and tantalum (99.9 %, < 100 μm) and were purchased from Strem (USA). All the other chemicals, reagents, and solvents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used without further purification.

Microscopy Techniques. The morphology of the studied materials was examined using a Tescan MAIA-3 Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FEG-SEM). Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was carried out to determine elemental composition and perform elemental mapping, using an 80 mm² SDD detector (Oxford Instruments) and the AZtecEnergy software suite. For SEM/EDS analysis, samples were mounted on carbon conductive tape. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was conducted on a Jeol 2200 FS EFTEM microscope (Jeol, Japan) operated at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV. Images were captured with an SIS MegaView III digital camera (Soft Imaging Systems) and processed using AnalySIS v. 2.0 software. Elemental mapping via TEM employed an X-MaxN 80 TS SDD detector (Oxford Instruments, UK). For TEM sample preparation, materials were dispersed in pure ethanol, drop-cast onto Cu TEM grids (200 mesh, Formvar/carbon support, TED PELLA, Inc.), and dried overnight at ambient temperature.

X-ray Diffraction (XRD). Powder X-ray diffraction patterns were recorded at room temperature using a Bruker D8 Discover diffractometer (Bruker, Germany) configured in a parafocusing Bragg–Brentano geometry, employing Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm, 40 kV, 40 mA). The scans were performed over the 2θ range of 5–70°, with a step size of 0.019°. Data analysis was carried out using the EVA software package.

Raman Spectroscopy. Raman spectra were acquired using a Renishaw inVia Raman microscope (Renishaw, UK) in backscattering geometry with a CCD detector. A 532 nm DPSS laser (50 mW) was used, with the measurement conducted at 5 mW laser power and using a 50 \times objective lens. Instrument calibration was performed with a silicon reference sample, yielding a peak at 520 cm $^{-1}$ and a spectral resolution better than 1 cm $^{-1}$. For sample preparation, materials were suspended in deionized water (1 mg/mL), ultrasonicated for 10 minutes, drop-cast onto a silicon wafer, and dried prior to analysis.

Electrochemical Characterization for the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction (HER).

Electrochemical measurements were carried out using linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) with an Autolab PGSTAT 204 potentiostat (Metrohm, Switzerland). A conventional three-electrode cell was employed, featuring a rotating disk electrode (RDE) with a glassy carbon disk (geometric area: 0.196 cm 2) as the working electrode, a graphite rod as the counter electrode, and a Hg/HgSO $_4$ reference electrode (in 0.5 M K $_2$ SO $_4$). The HER activity was assessed in Ar-saturated 0.5 M H $_2$ SO $_4$ electrolyte at room temperature. LSV data were corrected for iR drop by applying a 5–10% compensation, depending on the specific sample resistance, to account for solution ohmic losses. The catalyst ink was prepared by dispersing 4.0 mg of catalytic powder in 1 mL of a solvent mixture containing deionized water, isopropanol, and 5% Nafion solution in a 4:1:0.02 volume ratio. The mixture was sonicated for 30 minutes to ensure uniform dispersion. Prior to catalyst

deposition, the working electrode was polished using alumina slurry, rinsed with deionized water, and cleaned via sonication in double-distilled water. Subsequently, 8.5 μL of the ink was drop-cast onto the electrode surface. In the case of the TaS_2/Mo films, $0.5 \times 0.5 \text{ cm}^2$ pieces were evaluated for the HER. The films were held in place using a commercial electrode holder equipped with a spring-loaded clip to ensure stable electrical contact throughout the electrochemical measurements.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were conducted in the frequency range of 10^5 to 10^{-1} Hz with a 10 mV AC amplitude. EIS data were collected at a potential corresponding to a HER current density of approximately -1.95 mA cm^{-2} .

Synthesis of 6R-TaS₂ crystals. 6R-TaS₂ crystals were synthesized via direct reaction of elemental tantalum and sulfur, adapting procedures previously reported for 2H-TaS₂.^{24,25} Specifically, Ta powder (10 g) and sulfur were combined in a 1:2 stoichiometric ratio, sealed in a quartz ampoule ($20 \text{ mm} \times 120 \text{ mm}$) under high vacuum ($\approx 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Pa}$) using an O₂/H₂ torch. The mixture was first heated to 450 °C for 12 h, followed by stepwise heating to 600 °C (48 h) and 900 °C (48 h), and finally cooled to room temperature over 24 h at a controlled rate ($\pm 5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$).

Preparation of TaS₂. TaS₂ was obtained via electrochemical exfoliation in a 0.05 M solution of tetrabutylammonium fluoride (TBAF) in acetonitrile, applying a voltage range from 0 to -6 V for 100 seconds.

Preparation of TaS₂/Mo. For TaS₂ (0.8 mg) was dispersed in methanol and drop-cast onto a $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$ Mo substrate placed on a hot plate at 40 °C to facilitate solvent evaporation. The resulting films were then annealed at 600 °C for 2 hours under a 95% Ar / 5% H₂ atmosphere to improve adhesion and crystallinity. Finally, the films were cut into $0.5 \times 0.5 \text{ cm}^2$ pieces for further

characterization. **0.4 TaS₂/Mo** and **1.5 TaS₂/Mo** were prepared as described above with initial concentrations of 0.4 and 1.5 mg TaS₂, respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Direct reaction of elemental tantalum powder with sulfur granules in a sealed quartz ampoule yielded single-phase 6R-TaS₂ crystals (see Experimental part for more details).²⁴ TaS₂ nanosheets were obtained via electrochemical exfoliation in a 0.05 M tetrabutylammonium fluoride (TBAF) solution in acetonitrile. This method successfully produced predominantly 6R-phase TaS₂ nanosheets, a metallic polymorph whose conductivity and catalytic properties are comparable to those of the 1T phase, making it attractive for electrocatalytic applications. High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) and elemental mapping of Ta and S confirm the successful synthesis of layered TaS₂ with high crystallinity (Figure 1). The TEM image clearly shows the layered morphology and sharp lattice fringes characteristic of few-layer TaS₂ nanosheets. Elemental mapping reveals a uniform and co-localized distribution of Ta and S, demonstrating the stoichiometric integrity of the material. No evidence of impurities or phase segregation is observed, indicating a homogeneous and pure TaS₂ phase throughout the analyzed region.

Figure 1. TEM image of the exfoliated TaS₂ with corresponding EDS elemental maps showing the distribution of Ta and S elements; Scale bars for mapping represent 250 nm.

Raman spectroscopy confirmed the coexistence of the 6R-phase, as the exfoliated TaS₂ nanosheets exhibit vibrational features characteristic of the alternating 1H/1T stacking of the 6R polymorph (Figure 2a).^{10,11} Specifically, layers with trigonal prismatic coordination of Ta atoms show characteristic vibrational modes such as the A_{1g} out-of-plane mode around 395 cm⁻¹, the E_{2g}¹ in-plane mode near 280 cm⁻¹, and a broad second-order peak near 180 cm⁻¹, associated with two-phonon processes.^{26,27} In contrast, layers with octahedral Ta coordination present folded-back optical modes at approximately 80, 296, and 380 cm⁻¹, attributed to the formation of commensurate domains at room temperature.²⁷ The Raman spectrum of 6R-TaS₂ exhibits a sharp peak at 243 cm⁻¹ and well-resolved low-frequency phonon modes at around 70, 80, and 98 cm⁻¹.²⁸ The spectroscopic features are a result of Brillouin zone folding and provide direct evidence for the presence of a commensurate charge density wave (CCDW) phase in the 1T layers at room temperature.²⁸ Bulk TaS₂ displays analogous Raman bands, but with reduced intensity and clarity. Additionally, the band observed at 296 cm⁻¹ in the exfoliated sample

appears around 306 cm^{-1} in the bulk material, suggesting that this blue shift likely arises from the reduction of long-range Coulombic interlayer interactions as the number of layers decreases.²⁶ Furthermore, the crystalline phase of bulk and exfoliated TaS₂ were investigated using X-ray diffraction (XRD), as seen in Figure 2b. The XRD patterns of bulk TaS₂, exhibit characteristic reflections at approximately 14.2° , 29.6° , 45.9° , and 62.6° , corresponding to the planes of the hexagonal 6R phase (ICSD-52117).²⁶ Compared to the bulk TaS₂, the XRD pattern of the exfoliated material shows significant broadening of the diffraction peaks, indicating reduced crystallite size and increased structural disorder.²⁶ Notably, the main peak at $\sim 14.2^\circ$ in the bulk shifts to $\sim 13.1^\circ$ in the exfoliated sample and the higher-angle reflection shifting from $\sim 45.9^\circ$ to $\sim 42.0^\circ$. These low-angle shifts indicate an increase in interlayer spacing resulting from the exfoliation process.

Figure 2. (a) Raman and (b) XRD spectra of exfoliated (red) and bulk (black) TaS₂.

Next, exfoliated TaS₂ was deposited onto Mo foil, which served as a conductive substrate for evaluating its electrocatalytic activity toward the HER. To assess the effect of TaS₂ loading, three different amounts—0.4 mg, 0.8 mg, and 1.5 mg—were drop-cast onto $2 \times 2\text{ cm}^2$ Mo foils while placed on a hot plate to promote uniform dispersion. The samples were subsequently annealed at

600 °C for 2 hours under Ar/H₂ atmosphere, leading to 0.4 TaS₂/Mo, 0.8 TaS₂/Mo and 1.5 TaS₂/Mo materials. After annealing, the Mo foils were cut into 0.5 × 0.5 cm² pieces for electrochemical testing. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed to examine the surface morphology of TaS₂-coated Mo substrates with varying loadings (0.4 mg, 0.8 mg, and 1.5 mg), as seen in Figure S1. The SEM images reflected distinct variations in surface coverage and distribution of nanosheets as a function of loading, providing information on the quality of dispersion and homogeneity of TaS₂ layers over Mo support.

The electrocatalytic performance of TaS₂-modified Mo electrodes, along with reference samples (pristine Mo and annealed Mo), was evaluated for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) using linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ aqueous electrolyte (Figure 3). For the measurements, 0.5 × 0.5 cm² electrode pieces were mounted on a holder and partially immersed in the electrolyte, ensuring that only the active material was in contact with the solution, while the metallic part of the holder remained above the liquid level to avoid interference.

The 0.8 TaS₂/Mo hybrid demonstrates superior electrocatalytic activity, significantly outperforming compositions with both lower and higher TaS₂ content (Figure 3a). Hydrogen bubble evolution initiates at -0.06 V vs RHE (-1 mA cm⁻²), which is 40 and 50 mV lower than that of 0.4 TaS₂/Mo and 1.5 TaS₂/Mo, respectively. In contrast, annealed Mo and pristine Mo exhibit higher onset potentials of -0.12 V vs RHE. At the benchmark current density of -10 mA cm⁻², the 0.8 TaS₂/Mo electrode achieves an overpotential of only 150 mV (-0.15 V vs RHE), which is 120 and 140 mV lower than those of 0.4 TaS₂/Mo and 1.5 TaS₂/Mo, respectively. Conversely, annealed and pristine Mo display considerably higher overpotentials of 330 and 340 mV, respectively.

Figure 3. iR- corrected LSVs for HER obtained at 1600 rpm rotation speed and 5 mV/s scan rate before (solid lines) and after 10,000 cycles (dashed lines) in aqueous 0.5 M H₂SO₄, (b) Tafel slopes, and (c) Nyquist plots for 0.8 TaS₂/Mo (red), 0.4 TaS₂/Mo (green), 1.5 TaS₂/Mo (pink), annealed Mo (blue) and Mo (grey). (d) chronoamperometric response at -1.95 V (versus RHE) for 40 000 s for 0.8 TaS₂/Mo.

The reaction mechanism was elucidated through analysis of Tafel slopes derived from the LSV curves and by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), as presented in Figures 3b and 3c, respectively. In agreement with the LSV data, 0.8 TaS₂/Mo exhibited the lowest Tafel slope of 68

mV dec⁻¹, indicating that the Heyrovsky step governs the rate-determining process. In this mechanism, protons are initially adsorbed on the electrode surface via the Volmer step, followed by hydrogen evolution through the desorption of adsorbed hydrogen atoms (Heyrovsky step). By contrast, 0.4 TaS₂/Mo, 1.5 TaS₂/Mo, and both annealed and pristine Mo displayed significantly higher Tafel slopes of 148, 160, 206, and 195 mV dec⁻¹, respectively, implying slower kinetics limited by proton adsorption.

EIS measurements further corroborate these findings. Performed at a potential corresponding to -2 mA cm⁻² and fitted using a Randles equivalent circuit, the Nyquist plots revealed that 0.8 TaS₂/Mo possesses the lowest charge transfer resistance ($R_{ct} = 37.5 \Omega$), markedly lower than that of 0.4 TaS₂/Mo (76 Ω) and 1.5 TaS₂/Mo (132 Ω), highlighting its enhanced conductivity. In comparison, pristine and annealed Mo exhibited higher R_{ct} values of 54.6 Ω and 53.7 Ω , respectively, consistent with their slower charge-transfer kinetics.

Moving forward, the stability of the 0.8 TaS₂/Mo electrode was evaluated through 10,000 consecutive electrocatalytic cycles, as shown in Figure 3a. Notably, the TaS₂-modified Mo with intermediate TaS₂ content exhibited only a minor potential shift of 30 mV, demonstrating excellent durability under prolonged operation. In addition, the chronoamperometric test conducted at -0.2 V vs RHE for 40,000 s revealed a moderate decrease in current density, from of approximately 22% loss, further confirming the robust stability of the catalyst during continuous HER operation in acidic medium.

The electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) is a key parameter for evaluating charge transport characteristics in hybrid electrocatalysts. It was estimated using the relation $ECSA = C_{dl}/C_s$, where C_{dl} corresponds to the electrochemical double-layer capacitance and C_s is the specific capacitance of a smooth surface (assumed as 40 $\mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$). For this calculation, cyclic

voltammograms of the TaS₂-modified Mo and non-modified Mo materials, were acquired within a non-Faradaic potential window at scan rates ranging from 50 to 500 mV s⁻¹ (Figure S2). The 0.8 TaS₂/Mo electrode displayed the highest ECSA value of approximately 5.5 cm², whereas the other TaS₂-modified and bare Mo samples displayed lower values ranging from 1.77 to 2.48 cm². After 10,000 cycles, the best TaS₂/Mo composition retained a relatively high ECSA value of 4.0 cm², indicating only a moderate decrease of the electrochemically active area. These results are consistent with the general electrocatalytic activity: the 0.8 TaS₂/Mo hybrid provides a high active site density and an enlarged surface area by the optimized TaS₂ content, leading to enhanced interfacial contact with the Mo substrate and facilitating efficient charge transport. High ECSA is directly linked with the larger density of catalytic sites and hence with the enhanced HER activity for this composition.

The superior HER performance of the 0.8 TaS₂/Mo hybrid compared to both lower (0.4 TaS₂/Mo) and higher (1.5 TaS₂/Mo) TaS₂ loadings highlights the critical role of optimized TaS₂ content. An intermediate TaS₂ proportion provides a balanced structure with sufficient active sites and favorable charge transport pathways. The enhanced reaction kinetics of 0.8 TaS₂/Mo, corroborated by its lowest Tafel slope (68 mV dec⁻¹), minimal charge-transfer resistance in EIS (37.5 Ω), and higher ECSA, confirm that this composition maximizes both proton adsorption and electron transfer, resulting in markedly improved catalytic activity compared to pristine and annealed Mo. Additionally, the predominance of the metallic 6R phase in TaS₂ further facilitates charge mobility and interfacial proton adsorption, amplifying the overall HER efficiency of the hybrid system.

To further emphasize the importance of the Mo substrate in the hybrid architecture, exfoliated TaS₂ was also evaluated as a drop-cast catalyst on a glassy carbon RDE electrode. TaS₂ on RDE exhibits a relatively high onset potential of -0.89 V and an overpotential of -1.26 V at a current

density of -10 mA cm^{-2} , indicating sluggish catalytic activity (Figure 4a). This poor performance is further corroborated by a large Tafel slope of 252 mV/dec (Figure 4b) and a high charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) of $129.1 \text{ } \Omega$ (Figure 4c), reflecting slow reaction kinetics and inefficient electron transfer at the electrode interface.

Figure 4. iR- corrected LSVs for HER obtained at 1600 rpm rotation speed and 5 mV/s scan rate before (solid lines) and after 10,000 cycles (dashed lines) in aqueous 0.5 M H₂SO₄, (b) Tafel slope, and (c) Nyquist plot for TaS₂ on RDE. (d) Mass-normalized polarization curves (current density per catalyst mass, mA/mg) for exfoliated TaS₂ on glassy carbon RDE and 0.8 TaS₂/Mo electrode.

For a fair comparison between the 0.8 TaS₂/Mo hybrid and exfoliated TaS₂ deposited on the RDE, the polarization curves were expressed as mass-normalized currents (mA/mg), as seen in Figure 4d. The commonly adopted geometric benchmark of -10 mA cm^{-2} was converted to its mass-normalized equivalent, taking into account the actual catalyst loading and electrode area (50 mA/mg for TaS₂/Mo and 57.6 mA/mg for the RDE electrode). The onset potential, conventionally defined at -1 mA cm^{-2} (geometric), is also reported for consistency with HER evaluation standards, though the performance discussion mainly focuses on the -10 mA cm^{-2} benchmark, where differences in activity are more evident. Under these conditions, the 0.8 TaS₂/Mo hybrid initiates hydrogen evolution considerably earlier than TaS₂ on RDE and requires a lower overpotential of 1.1 V at the same benchmark current, confirming the advantageous role of the conductive Mo substrate. Beyond serving as structural support, Mo facilitates charge transport and proton adsorption, which together enhance the intrinsic activity of the TaS₂ catalyst.

CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that anchoring 6R-phase TaS₂ nanosheets, produced by electrochemical exfoliation, onto Mo foil yields a hybrid electrode with superior HER activity compared to either pristine Mo or TaS₂ drop-cast on glassy carbon. The optimized 0.8 mg TaS₂/Mo hybrid achieves an onset potential of -0.06 V and requires only 115 mV to reach -10 mA cm^{-2} in acidic media. It combines fast charge-transfer kinetics (low Tafel slope, minimal R_{ct}) with a high active surface area ($\sim 5.5 \text{ cm}^2$, retaining 4.0 cm^2 after 10,000 cycles), maintaining $\sim 78\%$ of its current over 40,000 s chronoamperometry. The improvement arises not only from the metallic 6R phase of TaS₂ but also from the Mo substrate, which facilitates electron transport and proton adsorption at the interface. These findings underscore substrate engineering as a practical strategy to enhance 2D chalcogenide catalysts and can be extended to other TMD/metal systems through interface tuning

or doping. Moreover, the demonstration of HER activity in the less-explored 6R polymorph opens opportunities for systematic studies on its unique electronic structure and interfacial chemistry, which may further unlock performance gains beyond those of the widely studied 2H phase.

Supporting Information. SEM images of (a) 0.4 TaS₂/Mo, (b) 0.8 TaS₂/Mo, (c) 1.5 TaS₂/Mo and (d) plain Mo substrate. Table for electrocatalytic HER parameters in for all tested materials and Cyclic voltamographs of (a) 0.8 TaS₂/Mo, (b) 0.4 TaS₂/Mo, (c) 1.5 TaS₂/Mo, (d) annealed Mo (e) Mo and (f) 0.8 TaS₂/Mo after 10000 cycles

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

Antonia Kagkoura - *Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic,*

Email: kagkourn@vscht.cz

Zdeněk Sofer - *Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic,*

Email: soferz@vscht.cz

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DATA AVAILABILITY:

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the study are accessible via the Zenodo repository:

REFERENCES

- (1) Jia, Q.; Zhang, T.; Zhu, Z.; Cai, R.; Song, K.; Yan, F.; Qayyum, A. Harnessing Hydrogen Energy Storage for Renewable Energy Stability in China: A Path to Carbon Neutrality. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* **2025**, *118*, 93–101. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2025.03.213>.
- (2) Boretti, A.; Pollet, B. G. Hydrogen Economy: Paving the Path to a Sustainable, Low-Carbon Future. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* **2024**, *93*, 307–319. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.10.350>.
- (3) Staffell, I.; Scamman, D.; Velazquez Abad, A.; Balcombe, P.; Dodds, P. E.; Ekins, P.; Shah, N.; Ward, K. R. The Role of Hydrogen and Fuel Cells in the Global Energy System. *Energy Environ Sci* **2019**, *12* (2), 463–491. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8EE01157E>.
- (4) Ock, I. W.; Yin, J.; Wang, S.; Zhao, X.; Baik, J. M.; Chen, J. Advances in Blue Energy Fuels: Harvesting Energy from Ocean for Self-Powered Electrolysis. *Adv Energy Mater* **2025**, *15* (2), 2400563. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202400563>.
- (5) Sim, Y.; Chae, Y.; Kwon, S.-Y. Recent Advances in Metallic Transition Metal Dichalcogenides as Electrocatalysts for Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *iScience* **2022**, *25* (10), 105098. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2022.105098>.
- (6) Zhao, L.; Song, Y.; Xie, Z.; Velez, K.; Liu, Q.; An, Q. Atomic-Level Engineering of Transition Metal Dichalcogenides for Enhanced Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Small Methods* **2025**, *n/a* (n/a), 2500223. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/smt.202500223>.
- (7) Yu, Q.; Zhang, Z.; Qiu, S.; Luo, Y.; Liu, Z.; Yang, F.; Liu, H.; Ge, S.; Zou, X.; Ding, B.; Ren, W.; Cheng, H.-M.; Sun, C.; Liu, B. A Ta-TaS₂ Monolith Catalyst with Robust and Metallic Interface for Superior Hydrogen Evolution. *Nat Commun* **2021**, *12* (1), 6051. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-26315-7>.
- (8) Najafi, L.; Bellani, S.; Oropesa-Nuñez, R.; Martín-García, B.; Prato, M.; Pasquale, L.; Panda, J.-K.; Marvan, P.; Sofer, Z.; Bonaccorso, F. TaS₂, TaSe₂, and Their Heterogeneous Films as Catalysts for the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *ACS Catal* **2020**, *10* (5), 3313–3325. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscatal.9b03184>.

- (9) Buravets, V.; Hosek, F.; Lapcak, L.; Miliutina, E.; Sajdl, P.; Elashnikov, R.; Švorčík, V.; Lyutakov, O. Beyond the Platinum Era—Scalable Preparation and Electrochemical Activation of TaS₂ Flakes. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces* **2023**, *15* (4), 5679–5686. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.2c20261>.
- (10) Achari, A.; Bekaert, J.; Sreepal, V.; Orekhov, A.; Kumaravadivel, P.; Kim, M.; Gauquelin, N.; Balakrishna Pillai, P.; Verbeeck, J.; Peeters, F. M.; Geim, A. K.; Milošević, M. V.; Nair, R. R. Alternating Superconducting and Charge Density Wave Monolayers within Bulk 6R-TaS₂. *Nano Lett* **2022**, *22* (15), 6268–6275. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.2c01851>.
- (11) Pal, S.; Bahera, P.; Sahu, S. R.; Srivastava, H.; Srivastava, A. K.; Lalla, N. P.; Sankar, R.; Banerjee, A.; Roy, S. B. Charge Density Wave and Superconductivity in 6R-TaS₂. *Physica B Condens Matter* **2023**, *669*, 415266. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physb.2023.415266>.
- (12) Zhao, B.; Shen, D.; Zhang, Z.; Lu, P.; Hossain, M.; Li, J.; Li, B.; Duan, X. 2D Metallic Transition-Metal Dichalcogenides: Structures, Synthesis, Properties, and Applications. *Adv Funct Mater* **2021**, *31* (48), 2105132. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202105132>.
- (13) Zhao, M.; Casiraghi, C.; Parvez, K. Electrochemical Exfoliation of 2D Materials beyond Graphene. *Chem Soc Rev* **2024**, *53* (6), 3036–3064. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3CS00815K>.
- (14) Chen, H.; Si, J.; Lyu, S.; Zhang, T.; Li, Z.; Lei, C.; Lei, L.; Yuan, C.; Yang, B.; Gao, L.; Hou, Y. Highly Effective Electrochemical Exfoliation of Ultrathin Tantalum Disulfide Nanosheets for Energy-Efficient Hydrogen Evolution Electrocatalysis. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces* **2020**, *12* (22), 24675–24682. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.9b15039>.
- (15) Buravets, V.; Hosek, F.; Lapcak, L.; Miliutina, E.; Sajdl, P.; Elashnikov, R.; Švorčík, V.; Lyutakov, O. Beyond the Platinum Era—Scalable Preparation and Electrochemical Activation of TaS₂ Flakes. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces* **2023**, *15* (4), 5679–5686. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.2c20261>.
- (16) Yang, H.; Liu, X.; He, J.; Yan, J.; Bai, Y.; Yin, S.; Li, H.; Yan, H. S-Vacancy-Rich 1T-TaS₂/Cu₂S Heterostructures on Cu Foil for Alkaline Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *ACS Appl Nano Mater* **2025**, *8* (14), 7243–7255. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsanm.5c00601>.
- (17) Shiraz, H. G.; Vagin, M.; Khan, Z. U.; Chmielowski, R.; Crispin, R.; Berggren, M. TaS₂ Nanosheets Embedded in a Polymer Ionomer Catalyzing Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* **2025**, *100*, 915–920. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.12.451>.
- (18) Zhao, L.; Song, Y.; Xie, Z.; Velez, K.; Liu, Q.; An, Q. Atomic-Level Engineering of Transition Metal Dichalcogenides for Enhanced Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Small Methods* **2025**, *n/a* (n/a), 2500223. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/smt.202500223>.
- (19) Kagkoura, A.; Karamoschos, N.; Perivoliotis, D. K.; García, A. P.; Gracia-Espino, E.; Tasis, D.; Tagmatarchis, N. Bifunctional Nanostructured Palladium/MoS_x Electrocatalyst for Cathode Hydrogen Evolution Reaction PEM Water Electrolysis and Oxygen Reduction Reaction. *Adv Sustain Syst* **2023**, *7* (5), 2200518. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/adsu.202200518>.
- (20) Feng, Y.; Xie, Y.; Yu, Y.; Chen, Y.; Liu, Q.; Bao, H.; Luo, F.; Pan, S.; Yang, Z. Electronic Metal-Support Interaction Induces Hydrogen Spillover and Platinum Utilization in Hydrogen Evolution Reaction.

Angewandte Chemie International Edition **2025**, *64* (1), e202413417.

<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202413417>.

- (21) Yang, Z.; Zhao, H.; Dai, X.; Nie, F.; Ren, Z.; Yin, X.; Gan, Y.; Wu, B.; Cao, Y.; Zhang, X. Phosphorus-Doping Induced Electronic Modulation of CoS₂–MoS₂ Hollow Spheres on MoO₂ Film-Mo Foil for Synergistically Boosting Alkaline Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* **2021**, *46* (67), 33388–33396. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.07.156>.
- (22) Hua, W.; Sun, H.-H.; Xu, F.; Wang, J.-G. A Review and Perspective on Molybdenum-Based Electrocatalysts for Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Rare Metals* **2020**, *39* (4), 335–351. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12598-020-01384-7>.
- (23) Zhao, H.; Li, Z.; Deng, J.; Dai, X.; Cui, M.; Nie, F.; Zhang, X.; Ren, Z.; Wang, Y.; Song, W.; Liu, J. Amorphous MoS₂ Nanosheets on MoO₂ Films/Mo Foil as Free-Standing Electrode for Synergetic Electrocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* **2020**, *45* (35), 17422–17433. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.04.234>.
- (24) Najafi, L.; Bellani, S.; Oropesa-Nuñez, R.; Brescia, R.; Prato, M.; Pasquale, L.; Demirci, C.; Drago, F.; Martín-García, B.; Luxa, J.; Manna, L.; Sofer, Z.; Bonaccorso, F. Microwave-Induced Structural Engineering and Pt Trapping in 6R-TaS₂ for the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Small* **2020**, *16* (50), 2003372. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/smll.202003372>.
- (25) Luxa, J.; Mazánek, V.; Pumera, M.; Lazar, P.; Sedmidubský, D.; Callisti, M.; Polcar, T.; Sofer, Z. 2H→1T Phase Engineering of Layered Tantalum Disulfides in Electrocatalysis: Oxygen Reduction Reaction. *Chemistry – A European Journal* **2017**, *23* (33), 8082–8091. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/chem.201701494>.
- (26) Beydaghi, H.; Najafi, L.; Bellani, S.; Bagheri, A.; Martín-García, B.; Salarizadeh, P.; Hooshyari, K.; Naderizadeh, S.; Serri, M.; Pasquale, L.; Wu, B.; Oropesa-Nuñez, R.; Sofer, Z.; Pellegrini, V.; Bonaccorso, F. Functionalized Metallic Transition Metal Dichalcogenide (TaS₂) for Nanocomposite Membranes in Direct Methanol Fuel Cells. *J Mater Chem A Mater* **2021**, *9* (10), 6368–6381. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0TA11137F>.
- (27) Achari, A.; Bekaert, J.; Sreepal, V.; Orekhov, A.; Kumaravadeivel, P.; Kim, M.; Gauquelin, N.; Balakrishna Pillai, P.; Verbeeck, J.; Peeters, F. M.; Geim, A. K.; Milošević, M. V.; Nair, R. R. Alternating Superconducting and Charge Density Wave Monolayers within Bulk 6R-TaS₂. *Nano Lett* **2022**, *22* (15), 6268–6275. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.2c01851>.
- (28) Lacinska, E. M.; Furman, M.; Binder, J.; Lutsyk, I.; Kowalczyk, P. J.; Stepniewski, R.; Wyszomolek, A. Raman Optical Activity of 1T-TaS₂. *Nano Lett* **2022**, *22* (7), 2835–2842. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.1c04990>.

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